

EXAMINING THE LINK BETWEEN PARENTAL INVOLVEMENT AND ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF CHILDREN WITH INTELLECTUAL DISABILITY TOWARDS AN INTERVENTION PLAN

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Examining the Link Between Parental Involvement and Academic Performance of Children with Intellectual Disability towards an Intervention Plan

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Abstract

Involvement of parents is crucial in students' lives. The level of parental participation that a pupil receives at school and/or at home can influence how successful they will be in school. To better understand how parent involvement with children who have intellectual disabilities might improve their academic achievement, this research intended to raise parents' knowledge of it. The study used a correlational research approach, and the findings indicated that parental involvement in their children's learning performance while they are experiencing intellectual obstacles will always offer significant or exceptional relationships. Based on providing learners' improvements in their learning, the parental involvement or participations will supply an instant increase or well-supported advancement in some way. Meanwhile, it was discovered that the most frequent responses from the parents were as follows: parents watch over their children's screen time, playtime, and internet use; they make sure to have time to participate in their children's school activities; they attend every orientation the school calls for online/modular classes; and they are the kind of parents who place limits on what their children can and cannot do. Most of the parents who responded to the dichotomous questions about the performance of students with intellectual disabilities over the past three years agreed that there had been an improvement or rise in their children's performance. Many parents disagreed with the addition that there had been little to no progress made in their children's academic performance. This research focuses on strengthening the experience of families participating in the education of children with intellectual impairments and addresses the chances for families to engage in their children's learning journey.

Keywords: *parental involvement, academic performance, children with intellectual disability, learning performance*

Introduction

The best kind of parental involvement in their child's education, according to Bakken and Obiakor (2016), is dynamic, ongoing family interaction. Families have the right to choose the proper schools for their children as well as the level of participation they want to have. Parents take part in both activities at home and in their children's educational experience at school. Families must participate in the educational process if students are to learn well (Jafarov, 2015). Additionally, some experts think that parental participation helps improve children's academic abilities (Roberts & Webster, 2020).

According to research, including parents in the educational process is a good way to guarantee students' success (Barnard, 2004). Increased motivation, self-esteem, and self-reliance are just a few of the good benefits of parental participation on children outside of the classroom that may help them succeed academically regardless of their family's financial situation. Contrarily, research demonstrates that low levels of parental participation are a factor in both low student engagement and accomplishment (Bower & Griffin, 2011). In essence, rich learning environments may be created by parents, siblings, and other important relatives to improve children's academic development.

It is generally accepted that children who have their parents' unwavering love and support would work extra hard to meet high academic standards. Parents have an important influence in the academic success of their own children as well as the performance of the school (Lara & Saracosti, 2019). Involvement in education on an appropriate level is, in fact, an indication of high-quality instruction (Durisic & Bunijevac, 2017). However, there is still a substantial gap between theory and reality when it comes to the scholastic success of children with intellectual disability (ID), maybe as a result of the varying degrees of parental involvement from child to child.

Only a small amount of prior study examined the potential and difficulties associated with the engagement of parents of children with intellectual impairments, despite the fact that the problem of parents attending their child's public school being of rising relevance across the world. For instance, Viola and Daniel (2017) investigated the impact of parental participation on the development of intellectually disabled children attending specific institutions for skills training in Zambia.

According to the study, expectations, money, and education level all influence how likely parents are to be involved in their children's schooling. The study also discovered that parental engagement and whether it is enthusiastic and supportive have an impact on career advancement. This meant that in order to foster their children's growth, parents of children with intellectual disabilities should be involved in their schooling.

All students must be educated in the least restrictive environment possible, according to laws governing the provision of special education services to students with disabilities, such as the Individuals with Disabilities Education Act (IDEA, 2006) and No Child Left Behind (2001), and all stakeholders, including parents, must be given a voice. Even though parent engagement has been demonstrated to be a critical factor in student achievement, IEP teams are required to build an adequate educational plan to fulfill each

student's developmental and academic requirements (Murray et al., 2018). However, parents are frequently under involved in the process (Wilder, 2014; Pomerantz & Monti, 2015; Wang, 2014). According to a growing body of evidence, when parents of students with disabilities work successfully with the school, student learning results increase (Meadan, 2014). Studies also show that parents' engagement in their children's education not only helps them perform better, but it also gives them the high learning drive that is necessary for these learners. Additionally, parental participation fosters and cultivates a healthy relationship between parents and teachers and helps create a more acceptable and happy learning environment for children (Hsieh et al., 2012). Parents are children's first and most crucial teachers, it is necessary to remember this.

The school performance of children with ID was shown to be influenced by their parents in a more recent study by Ayoola and Edegbai (2019), and it was noted that there are several ways in which parents must support and encourage their children with ID. According to a recent research, parents of children with ID should try to fulfill their children's requirements, and school administration should give enough teaching resources to accommodate these children's circumstances and assist them learn and put the strategies they'll need to succeed academically into practice. Additionally, it was shown that parents had a significant influence on their children's academic success. Although the parents who participated in the study acknowledged that the teachers in question had adhered to state regulations in this regard, they made little reference to the parent-teacher relationship, suggesting that actions to strengthen the partnership between the school and the parents can enhance the experience of parents and teachers when creating an IEP. By supplying data to support the creation of IEPs to enhance the educational results of children with ID, this study assisted in the positive social change sought by experts in the field of education. According to studies, parents have a significant autonomous role in inspiring their children to learn (Gonzalez-DeHass, 2005).

The low intelligence quotient (below 70–75), which is typical of students with intellectual disabilities (ID), suggests that these students do not pick up academic and social skills as quickly as typically developing youngsters do. Therefore, learners with intellectual impairments come with significant assistance needs for intellectual functioning and adaptive behavior. Notably, its impairment impairs intellectual and cognitive abilities, which are essential for information acquisition. However, it has been demonstrated that one method to improve learning results for these students is by greater family participation. Furthermore, research has demonstrated a connection between parental participation, support, encouragement, and positive reinforcement and children's academic proficiency, a strong sense of self-worth, healthy social relationships, and fewer behavioral issues (Kurani et al., 2009).

Parental involvement is correlated with many educational constructs, including engagement, which includes participating in extracurricular activities, attending parent-teacher conferences, keeping track of students' grades, instilling parental values, assisting with homework, and offering both intrinsic and extrinsic motivation. Parental participation is crucial to the lives of our students. The level of parental participation that a pupil receives at school and/or at home can influence how successful they will be in school. In order to better understand how parent involvement with children who have intellectual disabilities may impact their academic achievement, this research tries to expand understanding of this topic. This will help to address how families may get involved in the educational process of their children and focuses on improving the experience of families involved in the education of children with intellectual impairments.

Research Questions

This study sought to determine the link between parental involvement and the academic performance of children with as a become a basis for an intervention plan. Specifically, it sought to answers the following questions:

1. To what extent do parents participate in their children's academic performance in terms of the following?
 - 1.1. support given at home;
 - 1.2. support given on school activities;
 - 1.3. financial and material support; and
 - 1.4. moral support?
2. What is the performance of learners with intellectual disability for the last three years?
3. Is there a significant relationship between parental involvement and performance of learners?
4. Based on the results, what intervention may be recommended?

Methodology

Research Design

This study used a correlational quantitative design that aims to identify, acknowledge, and analyze significant relationship between parental involvement and the academic achievement of children with intellectual disability in the School Year 2021 – 2022. The study included supports that have been applied by the parents/caregivers themselves to their children with intellectual disability which the results will become basis in creating an intervention plan.

Participants

Putting data in writing, this research utilized purposeful sampling method to determine the participants of the study through utilizing

questionnaires as the research method because this design enables researchers to tally objective results and to hear it straight from the research participants (parents) – their involvement in their child’s school matters. There are an estimated 150 voluntary parents of students with children with intellectual disability who are at aged around 7 years old. Location of the research is Zamboanga Sibugay where all of the respondents’ children are enrolled in.

Procedure

In seeking data from the respondents, an orientation to parent respondents was done prior to the distribution of the questionnaire. But before this, the researcher put in mind first the safety of the respondents by making sure that every protocol set forth must be followed so as not to harm the health and safety of the respondents. Procedures related to data gathering was done in one designated place or area.

The researcher had given the respondents ample time to respondents to answer the given questionnaire. The researcher committed that all information given by the respondents were taken cared with utmost confidentiality. Once data is already made available out of the responses retrieved from the target respondents, it was properly sealed and only upon the day of its analysis was opened to ensure that these data were known only to the researcher and to avoid being disclosed to the public unintentionally.

Data collected from respondents' responses was handled with the utmost confidentiality to ensure that the respondent's privacy is protected. Upon gathering of responses, the researcher tallied, analyzed and interpreted the results. No money, tokens, remuneration or incentives were given to the respondents all throughout the conduct of the study.

Data Analysis

In this study, the researcher used appropriate statistical tools to analyze the data gathered. To wit:

Frequency counts (f) and percentage (%) will be used to determine the socio- demographic profile of the respondents. Weighted Mean will be utilized to assess parental involvement among children with intellectual disability and their academic achievement. Multiple Regression Analysis was used for the significant relationship of the parental involvement among children with intellectual disability and their academic achievement: basis for an intervention plan.

Results and Discussion

This section comprises the results and discussions interpreted and analyzed systematically according to the statistical treatment to be applied in the study pertaining to the parental involvement among children with intellectual disability and their academic performance, which served as a basis for the intervention plan.

Table 1. The Descriptive Statistics on the Extent of the Parental Involvement on their Children's Academic Performance

Statements	5	4	3	2	1
<i>Table 1.1. Support Given At Home</i>					
1. I spend time helping my child with their homework every day.	35	47	39	16	13
2. I make sure my child has an area in the house just for his/her learning space.	31	58	37	14	10
3. I talk and communicate with my child daily.	50	61	24	12	3
4. I always check my child's homework to make sure it is correctly done.	36	42	33	27	2
5. I help my child build independence and set a daily routine.	33	50	38	19	10
6. I check for notes sent home by the teacher daily.	28	45	44	19	14
7. I practice my child to read and write and engage in active learning.	30	47	36	26	11
8. I monitor my child's television, playtime, and internet use	34	30	52	30	4
9. I demonstrate a positive attitude about education to my children.	26	62	42	11	8
10. I establish reasonable rules, making it clear to my child that he has to take responsibility for what he/she does.					
Total Frequencies	332	492	380	195	90
<i>Table 1.2. Support Given on School Activities</i>					
11. I always explain to my child the instruction in all activities.	30	52	43	18	7
12. I attend parent-teacher conferences and keep in touch with my child's teacher.	28	49	37	20	16
13. I think it is important to take my child to school activities and/or classroom parties.	47	72	18	12	1
14. I think it is important for my child's success that I go to school events or activities.	34	67	30	15	4
15. I volunteer at my child's school and/or join school's parent-teacher group.	31	47	44	20	8
16. I make sure to have time to be actively involved in my child's education by attending school activities involving parents and child.	23	34	46	28	19
17. I attend every orientation called by the school on online/modular classes.	25	43	54	16	12
18. I discuss with my child on reading materials given as a lesson.	38	62	27	15	8
19. I read the school newsletter to be well-informed of the activities for the good of my child.	24	49	46	18	13
20. I am always willing to help my child complete homework assignments.	69	72	5	3	1
Total Frequency	349	547	350	165	89
<i>Table 1.3. Financial and Material Support</i>					
21. I reward my child for good grades.	40	63	25	19	3

22. I provide my child materials for his/her projects and activities.	43	58	41	6	2
23. I give adequate allowance to my child for his/her personal needs and school matters.	26	60	34	13	17
24. I save money for my child's emergency expenses.	33	54	29	20	14
25. I support school projects.	44	49	45	7	5
Total Frequency	186	284	174	65	41
<i>Table 1.4. Moral Support</i>					
26. I talk and listen to my child without judgment and seeking to understand his/her concerns and challenges.	37	52	48	12	1
27. I always show my love for my child.	46	67	32	5	0
28. I encourage my child to pursue his/her goals for the future.	40	62	45	1	2
29. I encourage my child to do his/her best in school, hobbies and interests.	28	53	49	10	10
30. I acknowledge my child's achievements and supporting him/her through mistakes and challenges.	35	61	37	12	5
31. I am the kind of parent that sets the limit on what my child can do.	17	50	66	15	2
32. If my child gets upset when I say "No" I back down and give it to my child.	24	48	32	41	5
33. Together with my child, I set behavioral expectations and review them daily.	44	65	38	3	0
34. I treat my child fairly and develops a trusting relationship	51	72	25	1	1
35. Use positive words in giving encouragement and praises.	36	65	45	3	1
Total Frequency	358	595	417	103	27

Based on the frequency distributions on the Likert's Scale, majority from the questions told to the parents with children having their disabilities were under the most frequent responses of agreeing from the queries involved in the parental participations or involvement on their children's academic performance. Very remarkable from the most frequent responses from the different selected questions for the parents were as follows: parents monitor their children's television, playtime, and internet use, they made sure to have time to be actively involved in children's education by attending school activities involving parents and child, they attended every orientation called by the school on online/modular classes, and they were the kind of parent that sets the limit on what my child can do. This implies that majority of the parents were all hands – on in the welfare and the concerns pertaining to the academic performance of their children even if they have their disabilities.

Parental participation is the level of involvement a parent has in the education of their children. Parents may express reluctance to participate in their children's education, even though certain schools advocate good family involvement. It has been promoted in Western countries. However, a body of research has examined the effects of social and cultural variables as well as the outcomes of parental involvement and expectations on their children's development and learning (Bartolome et al., 2017).

Table 2. *The Performance of Learners with Intellectual Disability for the last Three Years*

Statements	1 (No)	2(Yes)
1. There is an increase or improvement in the performance of the learners with intellectual disability for the last three years.	14	136
2. There is a decrease or less improvement in the performance of the learners with intellectual disability for the last three years.	136	14
3. There is no improvement at all.	142	8

Based on the dichotomous responses on the performance of learners with intellectual disability for the last three years, majority of the parents agreed that there was an increase or improvements in the performance of their children with intellectual disability for the last three years. It has been appended and being supported by many of the parents as they disagreed that there were less, or nothing had been established improvements on their children's performance. This implies that parents still believe that there will always be a hope for their children having their mental disabilities to increase the level of performance of their capability and ability to learn regardless of the environment and even the status of the children's mental health conditions.

Studies show that as children become older, homework, parental involvement, and academic achievement all increase. Additionally, according to Carr (2013), parents who engaged in homeschooling activities may serve as positive reinforcers, providing adolescents the self-assurance they require for effective academic achievement. According to Sad and Gurbuzturk (2013), young children who have homework may experience long-term developmental effects. Furthermore, homework may develop good study habits, provide a positive outlook on education, and let students know that learning occurs outside of the classroom.

Table 3. *The Multiple Regression Analyses through Pearson R, Signifying the Correlation Between the Parental Involvement and the Learners' Performance*

Alpha	Degrees of Freedom	Critical Value	Computed R	Decision	Interpretation
0.05	148	0.1593	0.5789	Reject Ho	Significantly Related

Note: N=150 *Support Given at Home *Learners' Performance

Alpha	Degrees of Freedom	Critical Value	Computed R	Decision	Interpretation
0.05	148	0.1593	0.7888	Reject Ho	Significantly Related

Note: N=150 *Financia land Material Support *Learners' Performance

<i>Alpha</i>	<i>Degrees of Freedom</i>	<i>Critical Value</i>	<i>Computed R</i>	<i>Decision</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
0.05	148	0.1593	0.9030	Reject Ho	Significantly Related

*Note: N=150 *Moral Support *Learners' Performance*

<i>Alpha</i>	<i>Degrees of Freedom</i>	<i>Critical Value</i>	<i>Computed R</i>	<i>Decision</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
0.05	148	0.1593	0.9001	Reject Ho	Significantly Related

Note: N=150

Based on the multiple regression analyses on the Pearson's R for correlations, provided that the researcher aided with statistician's mandate to include the alpha error of 0.05, the degrees of freedom of 148, and the equivalent critical value of 0.1593, unanimously resulted in the rejection of the null hypothesis, signifying that there was a significant relationship between the parental involvement and the performance of the learners with intellectual disabilities. This implies that the parental involvement in the academic performance of their children in learning while having intellectual challenges will always give significant or remarkable associations on the affections of the two – interrelated variables involved. The parental involvement or participations will give immediate increase or well – supported advance somehow, on the basis in giving learners' improvements in their learning.

The Intervention Planning for the Parents with their Intellectually Challenged Learners

Preface

This school-based manual will be based on grouping mechanisms in an analytical fashion, so that advisors acquire their records including the frequency of visits to the school and the socio-economic status as the primary guide or recording mechanism to fill out the basic information of their learners. In accordance with this, advisors should carefully record the parent's explanations for any absences from their child's class or plans for collecting and distributing activity papers to their students. The advisers will gather their justifications as anecdotal recordings together with the socioeconomic analysis once the paperwork has been completed appropriately with theme annotations. The counselors will assemble these reasons as anecdotal recordings together with a summary of the socio-demographic profiles of the parents and students once the documentation has been completed in accordance with theme annotations, provided that the Data Privacy shall be deemed implemented.

Part 1: The Parental Involvement

The Chinese government and UNESCO collaborated to build the UNESCO International Research and Training Center for Rural Education (UNESCO INRULED), which opened its doors at BNU in 2008. In order to realize the aims of Education for All, UNESCO INRULED's vision is to promote social-economic development in rural regions by bringing about positive changes in rural residents' attitudes and behaviors. Rural residents make up the majority of the population in developing nations. Over 40 publications have been released by UNESCO INRULED, including research projects, training materials, periodicals, and newsletters. Additionally, UNESCO INRULED has developed a broad network of partnerships with UN agencies, foundations, non-governmental organizations, and development organizations in addition to developing direct connections with UNESCO institutions and centers. The UNESCO Institute for Information Technologies in Education (UNESCO IITE) was founded as a core component of UNESCO by the General Conference of UNESCO during its 29th session (November 1997), and it is based in Moscow, Russian Federation. The only Category 1 UNESCO Institute with a global mission for ICT in education is IITE. IITE has created its strategic focus areas in accordance with the new Education 2030 Agenda to meet the upcoming challenges and needs. IITE's new-age objective is to support creative ICT usage and function as a facilitator and enabler for the accomplishment of Sustainable Development Goal 4 (SDG 4) through ICT-enabled approaches and best practices.

One of the most important variables in a child's growth is their parents. This is because they have the power and ability, via their active participation in learning activities, to mold and grow their children into inspired, driven, and tolerant adults. On the other hand, parents who don't participate in their children's education are just seen as naively demotivating and demoralizing them. This in turn has a detrimental impact on their accomplishments (Naite, 2021).

Alampay (n.d.) claims that the majority of Filipino parents have authoritarian philosophies. Her research shows that the aforementioned cultural values of *kapwa* (helping others), *hiya* (shyness), and *utang na loob* (paying it forward) are among the interconnected themes that permeate the dynamics of Filipino parenting and parent-child relationships, which are characterized by children's respect for parental authority and obedience, family cohesion, and fulfilling familial obligations. Findings from her qualitative study on parenting in the Philippines suggest that in the years to come, Filipino parenting practices may change. Before developing new frameworks and regulations for parental engagement, it will be necessary to thoroughly assess the effects of these emerging ideas and actions on Filipino families and children's development.

The central government of our nation has launched the National Public Service Platform for Educational Resources as part of its effort to provide fundamental public services for education. The platform covers all educational levels and develops a network of interaction, collaboration, and application environments for resource suppliers and consumers. For teachers and students at all levels of education, a wealth of resources has been made available. These include problem sets and test databases for the high school entrance examination and the college entrance examination, as well as digital resources that are coordinated with classroom instruction in primary and secondary school (such as teaching plans, courseware, teaching videos, and course material). Additionally, the platform offers materials

for career education, safety education, moral education, physical education, health education, and art education to students, teachers, and principals of schools at all levels. The education sector of our state should swiftly build the National Network Cloud Platform for Primary and Secondary School based on National Public Service Platform for Educational Resources in order to assist the "Disrupted Classes, Undisrupted Learning" amid the coronavirus epidemic. The platform was updated with the necessary resources' modules covering 10 topics in time, including epidemic prevention education, moral education, curriculum learning, life and safety education, mental health education, family education, classic reading, trip learning education, film and television education, and electronic books, in order to meet the learning demands of the students during this particular period.

Materials included into a course's environment that assist students in meeting the course's stated learning objectives are referred to as "digital learning resources." These resources come in many different digital formats, such as graphics, pictures, music, video, simulations, animations, and prepared or programmed learning modules (Epigeum, 2019).

Furthermore, it is generally known that parents have a significant role in their children's growth and success, both within and outside of the classroom. Cooperation with parents is crucial for the implementation of modular distance learning to be successful. Parents nowadays facilitate learning at home. They are anticipated to act as "teachers" who support and mentor their students as they study at home. The above-mentioned epidemic caused the Philippines to experience a horrific new normal approximately two years ago. The fact that the education system's new normal has finally emerged thanks to what we dubbed the blended learning approach to remote learning is not concealed from our view. Due to the modular settings for the students and the involvement of their parents, this is the call on how to know the impact of the learning modality to the parents and students. This will be the experiences to be known as a phenomenological in finding a portfolio for the basis of making a school-based remodification of the learning modality. Due to unforeseen circumstances, the majority of students have had difficulty passing their modules and learning activity sheets. Parental participation in their children's learning performance in whatever learning modality they are currently using can help alleviate the stress that parents, who are our learners, are always under with their children.

Parents take on a heavy burden as learning continuity programs instruct children to learn at home. The engagement of parents plays a crucial role in the remote learning, which is intended to continue learning but this time inside the confines of the house, according to Brossard et al. (2020). As a result, decisions that affect remote education should take into account the requirement to guarantee that all parents can execute them. Manila Times (2020) praised parents for playing a significant part in establishing different remote learning modalities during the COVID-19 crisis in the context of Philippine education. With the start of the new school year, the Department of Education (2020) released a learning continuity plan. The use of remote learning in various modalities while taking into account the circumstances of the communities is one of the plan's provisions. Importantly, the strategy emphasizes the part parents play in putting its multiple learning delivery strategies into action (Pimentel-Tibon, 2020). For instance, it serves as a reminder that parents should strictly monitor their children's usage of computers in the early grades. Despite concerns about whether parents are prepared to take on this responsibility, it answers to the difficulty of orienting the parents. Struggles are unavoidable, despite efforts to support parents in this difficult work of homeschooling their children (Garbe et al., 2020).

The goal of this manual is to critically examine the strategies used by parents, particularly mothers, to give their engagement in their children's distant learning in the midst of the COVID-19 crisis significance. The study paper that goes along with this manual seeks to understand the fundamentals of parental participation amid the complexity of the modern world. In order to get deeper insights into the present state of education, it is important to examine the parents' actual experiences as they participate in their children's distant learning while the COVID-19 crisis is ongoing. For academics and researchers who are interested in the lived experience, particularly from the viewpoints of parents in the middle of one of the most catastrophic crises in human history, it will add fresh information. It will also give authorities, managers, and teachers useful information that they may use to build programs or initiatives that will meet the associated needs of parents and to guide future policy decisions.

Just adhere to these basic guidelines for parents to be more precise and succinct about what parental engagement means:

Parents shall be well – informed about school matters.

According to research-based documentation, the best indicator of parental involvement is for parents to be knowledgeable about school-related topics like learning modalities, while the worst indicator was for parents to consistently monitor their children's performance and take the teachers' and counselors' advice regarding matters involving their children's improvement.

Parents shall respond immediately in their children's academic performance.

The highest evidence of parental involvement showed that, from the perspective of the majority of learners, their parents were aware of and informed about school matters such as learning modalities. The lowest evidence of parental involvement showed that, from the perspective of the learners, that their parents are consistent in school appearance, which was descriptively supported.

Parents shall be consistent from numbers 1 and 2.

There is nothing wrong with consistently adhering to a certain concept or set of rules to improve students' academic achievement through increased parental participation as a result of evident-based phenomena or manifestations.

Part 2: The Learners' Performance

According to the research-based findings used to create this portfolio, there is a significant correlation between the level of parental involvement and the performance indicators, which means that the more parents get involved with their children's or learners' performance, the better off everyone ends up doing academically.

Due to the COVID-19 epidemic, face-to-face learning between students and teachers has been halted throughout the institution. The introduction of modular distance learning as an immediate reaction to maintain educational continuity has been made possible by this epidemic. The Philippines is currently in the process of adjusting to the new normal form of education, and the success of this process depends on educators' ongoing innovations and the active participation of other stakeholders.

The Philippines is currently in the process of adjusting to the new normal form of education, and the success of this process depends on educators' ongoing innovations and the active participation of other stakeholders. The Department of Education introduced Modular Distance Learning to maintain continuity in education and ensure that every school continues to fulfill its goal and vision, which is to offer high-quality instruction to every Filipino learner. Distance learning is a method of delivering education in which the teacher and the students interact while they are physically separated during teaching. There are three variations of this modality: TV/radio-based instruction, online distance learning, and modular distance learning. (Quinones, 2020) The most common kind of distance learning is modular learning. This also considers the needs of rural students who lack access to the internet for online education. The duty of keeping track of the students' progress falls on the teacher. The teacher may be contacted by the students by email, phone, text message, and instant messaging, among other methods. If at all practicable, the teacher should make home visits to students who require help or remediation (Llego, n.d.). Teachers will hand out printed modules to pupils, parents, or guardians directly or via local government representatives. The drawbacks include increased student self-motivation and self-discipline requirements, longer preparation times for teachers and staff, a lack of tangible incentives, and a larger demand on administrative resources to track students and run different modules.

One of the primary issues with the implementation of modular distance learning is the large number of activities in each module. In order to ensure that mastery is gained to the greatest extent feasible, the school should take this issue into consideration, limit the activities, and eliminate the unneeded themes. The less, the better, as several of the parents have stated. The students' lack of time to complete all the modules within a week is one of their main worries. As a result, a school must reduce the activities if it cannot prolong the time for completing the modules. We are all aware that mistakes occasionally cannot be prevented. Teachers should thus reassess the modules and ensure that all of the courses or activities are suitable for the learners' needs. The parents and pupils are both correct; each exercise's instructions must be simple enough for the learners to grasp. Lessons need to be clarified and teachers need to use more examples.

According to the useful findings of the performed research, there are some fundamental elements that greatly improve learner performance:

Reducing the number of activities in the modules and adding additional examples for each topic are among the approaches and strategies advised for the school to further enhance the modular distance learning. The Kumon Method will also be very beneficial for the talking modules in some of the recommended situations in other research-based outcomes (just a figure of speech).

Reduce/lessen activities in the modules and remove pointless exercises are the suggested solutions to the highlighted issues in modular distance learning that parents have raised concerns about the modules.

Part 3: The Advisers' Appended Functions

The school-based handbook is now thought of as the advisers' added responsibility to the modular classrooms they are already managing. Here are the advisers' suggested guidelines for completing the recently added function for the modular modality extremely well for the modular modality strategy:

Improvements in the academic performance of the learners will be based on grouping mechanisms in a manner that gives advisors access to records pertaining to the frequency of visits to the school and the socio-economic status as the fundamental guide or recording mechanism to complete the basic information of their learners.

The parents' explanations for absences from their child's day or the times they pick up and distribute activity sheets to their students should be properly recorded by advisors in accordance with socio-demographic profiles.

The counselors will assemble these reasons as anecdotal recordings together with a summary of the socio-demographic profiles of the parents and students once the documentation has been completed in accordance with theme annotations, provided that the Data Privacy shall be deemed implemented.

Part 4: The Building of The Strategy

Reflective practitioners include educators. The following strategies shall be the analytical and comprehensive principled methods or methodical way that can match from the parental involvement necessities based on the above stated guided principles of the newly

installed appendix for the functions on the modular classes to be shouldered by the teacher- advisers:

Alterations to the Manual. It is true that a material may not always serve as a trustworthy source or guiding principle; rather, it may just reflect the way things are going at the time the modular learning is taking place. The adviser should annotate the manual at this point. On the basis of the academic performance improvements of the modular learners while the parents are engaged in their competent learning, there are times when they need to accept the principles written here, or should we say there are times when they need to disregard some principles that are not appropriate for their current situations.

Grouping Mechanism. If the remodification process tends to follow the Quadronometric Modular Cooperative Learning principle, which was developed by the Filipino mathematician John Austin Mendoza, this will require more preparation and cooperation from the parents in the school to help those who are having trouble submitting their learning activity sheets or modules.

Anecdotal Records. When an adviser or teacher is adopting modular learning among the pupils, it is crucial to consider the importance of the record books they have gotten in order to do their job or function.

Although parents are involved everywhere, which is true, there is still a need to record anecdotes about any situations that have to do with issues with the submission of learning modules. Yes, without a doubt, with the help of the advice department.

Documentations. Additionally, the teacher or advisor has the chance to do various types of fundamental or action research with the help of their records of parental engagement in institutions that monitor students' performance. This is referred to as "documented preparations" to gather qualitative studies that advance the phenomena of doing research on parental participation and the learners' improvement in their academic performance while inside the modular premises.

Thematic Analyses. As was already indicated, the possibility for the teacher to undertake a fundamental or action research scenario will serve as a framework for thematically analyzing the negative effects or the beneficial results of incorporating parents in the development of their children's academic performance. Thematic analyses must take the shape of recorded and phenomenological replies from participants, who can be either parents, students, or even teachers who are currently dealing with the pressures of modular distributions.

Conclusion

Implications on the parents were all hands – on in the welfare and the concerns pertaining to the academic performance of their children even if they have their disabilities.

Parents still believe that there will always be a hope for their children having their mental disabilities to increase the level of performance of their capability and ability to learn regardless of the environment and even the status of the children's mental health conditions.

Parental inclusions on the performance of their children in learning while having intellectual challenges will always give significant or remarkable associations on the affections of the two – interrelated variables involved. The parental involvement or participations will give immediate increase or well – supported advancement somehow, on the basis in giving learners' improvements in their learning.

The lowest assessed on the frequency part of the survey was the statement pertaining to the parents who made sure to have time to be actively involved in their child's education by attending school activities involving parents and child.

It is preferred that the parents who were chosen for this study's study focus on the time schedules that need to be set aside to ensure that they get involved in the education or learning enhancement of their children, especially when it comes to the intellectual challenges that are related to or associated with them.

The scenario of the planning for the intervention schemes to aid the children to progress further should also contain the degree of performance of their competence and ability to study regardless of the surroundings and even the state of the children's mental health issues.

Only if the school immediately establishes a school-based management program to include in their agenda with this kind of intervention that can build portfolio-based brochures that can be dealt with in research-based functions will the parental involvement or participations give an immediate increase or well-supported advancement somehow, on the basis of giving learners' improvements in their learning.

The suggested course of action. The basic manual or recording device to fill out the essential data about their students should be recognized to be a religious need in their school. Following these guidelines, advisors should carefully record the parents' explanations for any absences from their child's class or their plans for retrieving and distributing work papers to students with intellectual disabilities. The counselors will assemble these reasons as anecdotal recordings together with a summary of the socio-demographic profiles of the parents and students once the documentation has been completed in accordance with theme annotations, provided that the Data Privacy shall be deemed implemented.

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